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Statistical analysis and current state of the Russian tourism market

KEYWORDS

tourism,
tourism sector,
statistical
analysis,
travel agencies,
tour operators

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The Russian tourism market, like the global one, is facing serious challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic and other factors. Additionally, in the current geopolitical context and amid travel restrictions, domestic tourism in Russia is of particular importance. The economic crisis, the level of income of the population, the exchange rate, and other financial indicators have a significant impact on tourist activity.

Aim of the article: to analyze the current state of the Russian tourism market.

Materials and methods. The materials included official statistics, specifically information from the Federal State Statistics Service, Rostourism, and other state bodies, which contained data on the number of tourists, income from tourism activities, and infrastructure. Methods: statistical analysis, including descriptive statistics and time series analysis, are employed to study the dynamics of tourism market indicators over time, identifying trends and predicting future changes.

Results. The analysis of statistical data by years allowed identifying and describing the main trends in the development of the tourism sector, the volume and cost of selling tourist packages. The structure of collective accommodation facilities showed their percentage during the study period and the change in their shares.

The leading destination for 2019-2021 was Turkey, accounting for 56.1% of the total Russian tourist flow. At the same time, domestic tourism is on the rise – the most popular regions of the Russian Federation for tourist trips in 2021, as in 2019 and 2020, are Krasnodar Krai, the Republic of Crimea, Moscow, and St. Petersburg.

Conclusion. The modern tourism sector in the Russian Federation is a highly effective means of generating revenue. It is a successful direction that combines interconnected and complementary sets of events, services, and products, which, together, create a whole experience and value for their visitors. Still, it is subject to external factors and is associated with numerous costs, depending on the tourist market served.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the article lies in the fact that the Russian tourism market, like the global one, faced significant challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic and other factors. Additionally, in the current geopolitical context and amid travel restrictions, domestic tourism in Russia is of particular importance. The economic crisis, the level of income of the population, the exchange rate, and other financial indicators have a significant impact on tourist activity.

Russia has great potential for the development of various types of tourism, ranging from beach and ecotourism to cultural, educational, and extreme sports tourism. At the same time, state support for implementing multiple measures in the tourism industry, including subsidies, tax incentives, and infrastructure development, is critical.

LITERATURE REVIEW

O. Y. Ermolovskaya et al. study the trends in the development of inbound tourism in the Russian Federation and develop a set of measures aimed at successfully restarting inbound tourism in the context of stabilization of the epidemiological situation. The authors assessed the dynamics of inbound tourist flows and flows to the Russian Federation, investigating factors that have both positive and negative impacts on the development of inbound tourist flows to Russia. The authors emphasize the need to strengthen state support for the development of inbound tourism [1].

E. G. Leonidova and M. A. Sidorov propose an approach to determining the volume of domestic tourism in Russia and assessed its dynamics from 2009 to 2020. Based on the use of intersectoral modeling, the authors determine the economic effects of a twofold increase in the number of trips around the country planned by 2035 [2].

U. V. Alola et al. study the determinants of inbound and outbound tourism in Russia. According to the authors, both negative and positive shocks to business confidence and the consumer price index have a positive impact on international arrivals in Russia in the short and long term. Shock (regardless of direction) leads to lower international arrivals in the short and long term. We also found that the shock (mostly negative) of consumer confidence reduces the number of Russian travelers to foreign tourist destinations in the short and long term [3].

R. M. Melnikov and P. Y. Makarov test the hypothesis about the impact of territory branding initiatives on the number of tourists attracted and the income of the

tourist and recreational sector in the constituent entities of the Russian Federation. According to the authors, implementation of initiatives for branding territories is associated with an average increase in the number of attracted tourists by 15.7%, and the level of income from tourism services increases significantly with a more dynamic brand promotion policy. The authors believe that to achieve long-term goals of improving the income of the tourist and recreational sector in the region, not only branding of territories is required but also more capital-intensive measures to develop tourist infrastructure, create new facilities, and conduct events that could become an incentive to visit the region [4].

V. V. Lavrov considers the formation of an integrated digital platform, "Tourism and Travel", proposed by the author, as one option for adapting the tourism sector to new economic conditions. The author presents a model of a tourist route of personal choice as an illustration of the work of this platform [5].

A significant number of studies is devoted to the development of regional tourism in the Russian Federation, which requires an integrated approach that takes into account the unique characteristics of each region, investments in infrastructure and marketing, as well as state support.

E. M. Kryukova et al. study the prospects for the development of the Russian tourism economy in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the authors, the main problems hindering the development of the tourism industry in the regions include: the high cost of hotel services, the discrepancy between their price and quality; transport problem; low level of personnel qualification and, as a result, service; ineffective branding of regions or its absence [6].

V. S. Khetagurova et al. give recommendations on optimizing the rational use of specially protected natural areas for the effective development of ecological tourism in Russia. The authors propose a selection of territories for the priority development of environmental tourism, with preference given to federal protected areas that have high tourist and recreational potential. The method proposed by the authors for complex assessment of indicators enables the unification of the system of indicators for different types of protected areas, allowing for the analysis of the state of various functional zones under different anthropogenic loads [7].

E. G. Kropinova et al. believe that the Baltic macroregion is one of the developed and dynamically (albeit with difficulties characteristic of 2020-2023) growing tourist regions that attract the attention of researchers. The authors revealed that the rich

natural, cultural, and historical potential of the Baltic territories of the Baltic countries led to positive dynamics in the development of tourism infrastructure in general and tourist flows, including domestic tourism [8].

A. V. Belova & I. V. Fedina-Zhurbina believe that Kaliningrad Oblast has great potential for rehabilitation and health tourism. According to the authors, tourist flows to the Kaliningrad region increased from 2019 to 2021, when restrictions related to COVID-19 began, and requests for services provided by sanatoriums and rehabilitation centers in the Kaliningrad region also increased due to the pandemic [9].

I. Kedrova et al. note the increased attention of tourists to Rostov Oblast. The potential of Rostov Oblast is such that it enables you to become a member of the All-Russian Accelerator of Industrial Tourism. The authors believe that the production mechanisms, as well as the stories of the companies themselves, are very interesting and capable of opening the Don Territory from an entirely new side [10].

V. Provotorina et al. analyze the market of hotel and restaurant services in the context of urban districts and districts of Rostov Oblast, and provided a definition of services at enterprises in the catering industry and hotel service. The authors highlight the importance and expediency of developing accommodation and nutrition as a component of rural tourism infrastructure in Rostov Oblast, which can contribute to the region's social infrastructure development and the resolution of critical socio-economic problems in the Don region [11].

M. Finko and M. Kicha discuss the problems of rural tourism development, using the example of modeling the creation processes and prospects for implementing the Don Living Villages Ecosystem project. According to the authors, it is necessary to develop the potential of rural tourism as an effective and powerful tool for "revitalizing" rural areas to attract young people to live in rural areas [12].

E. I. Makrinova et al. study the features and challenges of agritourism development and developed an algorithm for its marketing support using digital tools. The authors systematize the factors hindering the growth of agritourism and identified digital tools for its development [13].

T. Agafonova and L. Spektor address the legal aspects of agritourism regulation. The authors believe that rural tourism can be considered a source of income for rural residents, which can serve as a catalyst for the development of various areas within the agro-industrial complex [14].

A. F. Eremeeva and Y. V. Elizarova believe that tourism is one of the promising areas of socio-economic development of the Russian Arctic. The authors propose

a typology of Arctic tourist complexes based on three key factors: types of Arctic tourism, the urban settlement system that has evolved in the Arctic, and environmental factors. Favorable opportunities for the systemic functioning of the network of tourist complexes, including “support centers”, “base cities”, and those located in natural settings, are indicated [15].

A. Yangutova et al. believe that the sustainable use of Mongolian ethnocultural tourist resources is of great importance in the promising and developing regional tourism market. The authors reveal the spatial structure of Mongolian ethnocultural tourist resources in the Republic of Buryatia. According to the authors, Mongolian ethnocultural tourist resources in the Republic of Buryatia can be classified into six types and 23 subtypes, with their spatial distribution structure aligning along Lake Baikal and the main transport routes [16].

E. V. Mikhailova examines cross-border tourism and changes in the tourism industry that have occurred on the Russian-Chinese border since 2014. The author demonstrates that, following the ruble’s devaluation in 2014, Russian and Chinese border cities adjusted their services to cater to Chinese tourists. The author concludes that an earlier reorientation towards domestic tourists (after 2014) allowed Heihe and Fuyuan to be more prepared for the next external shock. The tourism industries of Blagoveshchensk and Khabarovsk suffered significant losses, finding themselves in a situation of high uncertainty, in which it was impossible to predict the timing of the resumption of Chinese tourist arrivals [17].

Z. G. Mirzekhanova notes that, given the Far East’s geographical location and size, developing interregional ties is crucial for shaping cluster policy, which is currently underrepresented. The author proposes a model of the federal tourist interregional scheme for territorial-spatial planning, focusing on the creation of a comprehensive plan for tourism development [18].

A. Kuchumov et al. write that the experiences of Bulgaria, Germany, and China demonstrate that digitalization of tourism occurs in each country, albeit at varying speeds and relying on different indicators. The correlation between the calculated regional digitalization index and the number of tourists accommodated in hotels shows a direct strong connection, made it possible to predict the development of tourism through digital processes, formulate strategic plans for the development of the industry, taking into account modern digital tools, and calculate effective measures of state support and financing [19].

T. B. Klimova et al. assign a special role to digitalization in the system of forming consumer loyalty. According to the authors, the tourism ecosystem should integrate a range of digital solutions to promote domestic tourism products through tourist marketplaces, multilingual services, augmented reality, big data, artificial intelligence, chatbots, super applications, and other advanced services [20].

Y. Osipova and L. Kazmina believe that, due to the considerable involvement of both human and production resources in the tourism sector, this industry cannot remain without special legal, organizational, and economic means of influence, namely, public administration. The authors identify the primary areas of tourist activity, which contribute to both the development of domestic regional tourism and the support of Russian tourists. The authors pay special attention to state support for tourist activities in Russia, particularly the Tourist Cashback program, which aims to stimulate domestic tourist trips [21].

Special attention is also paid to studies on the development of inbound medical tourism in the Russian Federation [22], the development of film tourism as a promising area of intensification of tourist activity based on the development of a new tourist product related to filming locations for popular films [23], the development of river cruise tourism in Russia [24], as well as the development of medical and ecological tourism [25].

Therefore, to comprehend the current state of the tourism market in Russia, it is essential to gather and analyze data on tourist flows, tourism revenue, infrastructure, and other pertinent indicators. It is necessary to develop new approaches and models describing the current state and prospects for the development of the Russian tourism market. The results of research on the tourism market can contribute to the development of tourism theory, economics, and management, as well as offer practical recommendations for increasing the efficiency and sustainability of the tourism industry in Russia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials included official statistics, specifically information from the Federal State Statistics Service, Rostourism, and other state bodies, which contained data on the number of tourists, income from tourism activities, and infrastructure, and articles published in peer-reviewed periodicals: Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, Studies on Russian Economic Development, Journal for Global Business and Community, Regional Research of Russia, Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, Geography and Natural Resources.

Methods: statistical analysis, including descriptive statistics and time series analysis, are employed to study the dynamics of tourism market indicators over time, identifying trends and predicting future changes.

RESULTS

Modern economic development cannot be imagined without considering the processes of globalization, which impact all segments of the global economy, including tourism. In a relatively short period, tourism has become a global phenomenon, as evidenced by the large number of participants involved in international trends. We can say that the process of globalizing the tourist market is, in fact, the process of internationalizing tourist and hotel activities. Namely, under the influence of globalization, modern tourists have new needs, and the tourist offer diversified its activities within and outside the tourist economy to meet these requests.

Figure 1 Volume of services of travel agencies, tour operators, and other booking services and related services in the share of the gross added value of the tourism industry in the GDP of the Russian Federation

Source: compiled by the author based on Rosstat data

The tourism industry makes a significant contribution to economic growth. According to the Federal State Statistics Service, in 2021, the number of travel companies engaged in tour operator and travel agent activities totaled 13,076 units, with an average of 1.16 million employees (excluding small businesses). The share of the gross value added of the tourism industry in the gross domestic product of the Russian Federation in 2021 was 2,6%, up 0.2% from 2020, with the volume of services of travel agencies, tour operators and other booking services and related services in 2021 149,8 billion rubles, which is 1.63 times more since 2020. The average annual increase in the tourism sector of the Russian Federation from 2014 to 2019, before the onset of the pandemic, was 4.06% and remained at a reasonably stable level (see Fig. 1).

The volatility and decrease in the share of gross added value of the tourism industry in the gross domestic product of the Russian Federation in the period from 2014 to 2019 was caused by the uncompetitive pricing policy of tourist services in the Russian Federation, namely, the quality of the services provided does not meet consumer expectations. In 2020, the coronavirus pandemic and the quarantine measures implemented in regions affected all sectors of the Russian economy, particularly the tourism industry. The closure of international and domestic borders, the emergence of new standards of sanitation and hygiene in the industry, a decrease in demand for group travel and package tours, and a reduction in staff in travel industry companies led to a crisis in the tourism industry. In this regard, the share of the tourism industry's gross value added in the Russian Federation's gross domestic product in 2020 decreased by 0.1 percentage points compared to 2019 and amounted to 2.4%.

During the pandemic, the role of the buffer in the tourism sector belonged to government measures, which included:

- providing subsidies to tour operators for reimbursement of costs associated with air transportation;
- subsidizing small and medium-sized businesses and socially oriented firms to carry out measures to prevent SARS-CoV-2;
- interest-free lending to legal entities and individual entrepreneurs to pay salaries to employees and resume activities;
- prohibiting application of tax sanctions;
- extending licenses and permits for activities, etc.

Thanks to both cultural and other offers, the tourism sector of the Russian Federation manages to adapt to restrictions, changing conditions, and follow what modern “travelers” ask. When it comes to tourism development, the need to personalize approaches to tourist products and services is increasingly being imposed today. Success is mainly due to those forms of manifestation that have managed to shape their proposal by presenting authentic lifestyles, customs, gastronomy, surrounding values, the soul of the place, and inherited heritage.

Let us consider the dynamics of inbound and outbound tourist trips for the period from 2014 to 2021 across Russia (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Dynamics of the number of inbound/outbound tourist trips, thousand units

Source: compiled by the author based on Rosstat data

Figure 2 shows that, since 2014, the number of outbound tourist trips has exceeded the number of inbound tourist trips. This indicates that more money is taken out of the country than is attracted by tourist expenses. The main peak of outbound tourist trips occurred in 2019, with 45,330 thousand visits.

The leading destination in 2019-2021 was Turkey, accounting for 56.1% of the Russian tourist flow in 2021 (see Fig. 3).

At the same time, domestic tourism is on the rise. The most popular regions of the Russian Federation in 2021 for tourist trips, both in 2019 and 2020, were Krasnodar Krai, the Republic of Crimea, Moscow, and St. Petersburg (see Fig. 4).

Figure 3 Structure of Russian tourists by countries (% of the total number)
 Source: compiled by the author based on Rosstat data

Figure 4 Structure of Russian tourists sent on tours in the Russian Federation
 (as a percentage of the total number of tourists)
 Source: compiled by the author based on Rosstat data

Analyzing the tourism sector by regions of the Russian Federation, we can say that the volatility of growth rates in regions specializing in tourism is higher than the average in other regions of the Russian Federation. However, growth is similarly observed in other regions of the country in 2021.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The analysis of statistical data by years allowed identifying and describing the main trends in the development of the tourism sector, the volume and cost of selling tourist packages. The structure of collective accommodation facilities showed their percentage during the study period and the change in their shares.

It can be concluded that the modern tourism sector in the Russian Federation is an effective means of generating revenue and a successful direction that combines interconnected and complementary sets of events, services, and products, which, together, create a whole experience and value for its visitors. Still, at the same time, it is subject to external factors and is associated with numerous costs depending on the tourist market served.

An analysis of the current state of the tourism market enables the identification of the most popular destinations and tourist preferences, which in turn contributes to the development of infrastructure and the creation of new tourist products.

Based on statistical data, it is necessary to predict the demand for tourism services, which helps enterprises in the tourism industry plan their activities and optimize resources. The analysis of statistical data is necessary to assess the effectiveness of government support measures for the tourism industry and their impact on the market, which contributes to a more targeted and efficient use of resources. Analysis of data on tourist preferences and behavior will help identify weaknesses in the quality of services and infrastructure, which can contribute to their improvement and increase the level of tourist satisfaction.

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